

A Heat Pump Optimization-based Scheduling to Minimize Energy Cost and Ensure Thermal Comfort

Nearchos Stylianides, Lysandros Tziouvani, Stelios Timotheou, Lenos Hadjidemetriou
KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence and Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Cyprus
Nicosia, Cyprus
{stylianidis.nearchos, tziouvani.lysandros, timotheou.stelios, hadjidemetriou.lenos}@ucy.ac.cy

Abstract—This paper presents a novel optimization framework designed to minimize residential heating costs while maintaining occupant thermal comfort. The proposed method employs a data-driven learning algorithm to identify the parameters of a linear building thermal model. The identified thermal model is incorporated into a mixed-integer linear programming formulation, enabling discrete *on/off* control of the underfloor heat pump system while accounting for dynamic electricity pricing and user comfort constraints. A dual-band comfort model is implemented using soft constraints to balance occupant comfort and electricity cost while ensuring solution’s feasibility. The proposed framework is tested in a simulation environment that emulates the electrical and thermal behavior of a real residential building equipped with a heat-pump system. The proposed dynamic scheduling is compared against two static scheduling scenarios, indicating that the optimization-based strategy can significantly enhance thermal comfort while reducing electricity costs.

Keywords— energy cost, energy management, optimization, thermal dynamics, thermal comfort.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition towards smarter and more sustainable energy usage in buildings increasingly involves integrated energy management strategies that span multiple domains, including electricity consumption and heating/cooling systems. This cross-sectoral integration offers considerable potential for reducing energy costs, enhancing efficiency, and improving occupant comfort [1]. Such integrated management schemes are particularly well suited to buildings with underfloor, electricity-based heat pump systems, which are characterized by high thermal inertia and provide favorable dynamics for flexibility.

Achieving these goals requires solving complex multi-objective optimization problems that balance competing objectives, such as minimizing energy costs and maximizing occupant thermal comfort, while ensuring all operational constraints [2]. These challenges are further compounded by external factors such as forecasted weather conditions, variable time-of-use electricity tariffs, and the intermittent nature of renewable resources like photovoltaics (PV) [3]. Moreover, cross-sector energy management solutions demand comprehensive optimization approaches that rely on accurate modeling of building thermal dynamics, an aspect that is typically unknown and requires considerable effort to model individually for each building.

The work is supported by the Republic of Cyprus and the Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation under grant agreement CODEVELOP-REPowerEU/1223/0078 (ANTS), through the European Union’s NextGenerationEU initiative and the Recovery and Resilience Plan of Cyprus (Cyprus - Tomorrow). The work is also funded by the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101075747 (TRANSIT).

In this context, accurate thermal modeling is essential for predicting indoor environmental conditions, while also enabling informed decision-making and optimization-based scheduling. Such thermal models can be integrated into optimization-based scheduling or model predictive control (MPC) approaches to manage buildings’ thermal and energy performance [4]. These models are separated in three categories: (a) the detailed physics-based models, also called white box models, that generate accurate solutions but increase the complexity of the resulting optimization problems, which are hard to solve because these models are nonlinear and non-convex [5]; (b) non-transparent black box models that are based on machine learning algorithms and historical data, that are deployed easily but often lack generalizability and interpretability [6]; and (c) combined grey box models that include physical insights with empirical data, balancing complexity and usability, making them suitable for real-time, interpretable applications [7].

Resistance-capacitance (RC) models are commonly used in grey-box modeling to capture building thermal dynamics, varying in complexity from simple linear forms (e.g., 1R1C) to more detailed forms (e.g., 2R2C, 3R2C, 5R3C) [8]. While higher-order models offer improved accuracy, they require detailed physical parameters and extensive sensor data, often unavailable in practice, limiting their scalability in residential settings. Among reduced-order models, the 1R1C structure offers a practical balance between simplicity and predictive accuracy, making it well suited for control and optimization tasks [9]. However, a key challenge that remains is the identification of the model’s unknown parameters through data-driven learning approaches.

Beyond thermal modeling, a central objective in building energy management is to reduce electricity costs while satisfying occupant comfort. To this end, a variety of optimization techniques have been proposed for scheduling thermal system operations [10]. Bianchini et al. [11] developed an MPC approach for optimizing Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) operations, targeting both energy and cost efficiency. Similarly, Eini and Abdelwahed [12] introduced a distributed MPC for multi-zone buildings, aiming to maintain zone temperatures at desired levels while minimizing HVAC operating costs. However, both works focus on conventional HVAC systems, which typically lack significant thermal inertia, unlike underfloor heat pump setups, thereby limiting their ability to support flexible energy management over hourly or day-ahead horizons. Thorsteinsson et al. [13] introduced a price-responsive hierarchical MPC strategy for demand-side management, tested on a commercial heat pump system. Their controller shifts heating loads based on electricity price

signals, effectively reducing cost. However, the formulation relies on a single-objective optimization that prioritizes cost, while thermal comfort is enforced through hard temperature constraints. These hard constraints restrict the model's practicality, particularly in real-world scenarios where initial indoor temperatures may fall outside the defined bounds, potentially resulting in infeasible solutions. Introducing temperature soft constraints would offer a more flexible way to control comfort, ensuring feasibility while enabling better trade-offs between energy cost reduction and occupant well-being. Other studies have explored multi-objective control strategies using learning-based methods. For example, Schmitz et al. [14] applied reinforcement learning to optimize heating operations under cost and comfort considerations. While their method performs well, it requires large volumes of high-resolution training data and offers limited interpretability, making it less practical in data-constrained environments or applications requiring transparency.

Despite advances in building energy optimization, key challenges persist, particularly in residential settings. Many approaches assume known thermal dynamics and require extensive sensing infrastructure, which is rarely available in practice, and often enforce comfort through rigid temperature constraints that may lead to infeasible solutions. Others rely on data-intensive black-box models that lack interpretability. These limitations highlight the need for data-efficient, transparent methods that can learn building dynamics from limited data while ensuring feasible, cost-effective, and comfort-aware operation.

In response, this work proposes an optimization framework that integrates a simplified 1R1C thermal model with a multiple linear regression (MLR) algorithm to learn thermal dynamics from available building operation measurements and weather station data. The identified model is integrated into a new mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) formulation that minimizes both electricity cost and thermal discomfort. In the proposed optimization scheme, a dual-band comfort model with soft constraints is used to ensure feasibility, while the formulation excludes unnecessary constraints for improved computational efficiency and includes additional constraints to reflect real heat pump operational behavior. The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- A data-driven learning method to estimate the parameters of a linear thermal model using typically available indoor temperature, weather, and heating consumption data.
- An efficient MILP optimization scheme for heat pump scheduling in residential buildings that minimizes electricity cost, ensures occupant comfort, maintains feasibility, and incorporates realistic heat pump features.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. The problem statement is provided in Section II, while Section III presents the proposed methodology for smart buildings to effectively minimize electricity cost and maintain occupants' comfort. The solution is evaluated in Section IV, while Section V presents the conclusions and future work.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

This section begins by formulating the core problem of managing building electricity use and thermal comfort in residential buildings. The objective is to minimize the electricity cost based on imported P_t^i and exported P_t^e power (decision variables, in kW), and corresponding electricity prices c_t^i and c_t^e (inputs, in €/kWh), at each time step $t \in \mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, T\}$. Such an objective function is formulated as,

$$\text{minimize } \Delta T \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (c_t^i P_t^i - c_t^e P_t^e) \quad (1)$$

where ΔT denotes the time-step duration in hours. Non-convex complementarity constraints are used to ensure non-simultaneous power import and export, defined as,

$$P_t^i \cdot P_t^e = 0, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (2)$$

The building's power balance equation is given by (3),

$$P_t^i + P_t^g = P_t^d + P_t^e + P_t^h, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (3)$$

where variable P_t^h in kW denotes the heating power which is the electrical power consumption of the heat pump. Constants P_t^g and P_t^d denote the PV generation and load demand in KW. The heating power is limited by the nominal power of the heat pump \bar{P}^h , as specified in (4).

$$0 \leq P_t^h \leq \bar{P}^h, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (4)$$

To satisfy thermal comfort while managing the heating system, the indoor temperature T_{t+1}^i must be estimated at each step based on a thermal model. Such a model should consider weather conditions (e.g., outdoor temperature T_t^o), previous indoor temperature T_t^i , and heating power P_t^h , defined as,

$$T_{t+1}^i = f(T_t^i, T_t^o, P_t^h), \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (5)$$

The constraint that restrains the indoor temperature within its minimum \underline{T}^h and maximum \bar{T}^h limits is given by,

$$\underline{T}^h \leq T_t^i \leq \bar{T}^h, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (6)$$

Problem (1)-(6) is hard to solve and hence unsuitable for an effective management of electricity cost and thermal comfort due to the complementarity constraints (2) and unknown thermal modeling dynamics in (5). Moreover, potential feasibility issues may occur due to hard temperature constraints in (6). These issues are addressed in Section III.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This section presents an enhanced data-driven learning and MILP-based optimization framework for practical and effective management of electricity cost and thermal comfort in residential buildings. Section III.A describes the learning algorithm used to identify the building's thermal model parameters, while Section III.B introduces the optimization-based scheduling scheme, modified to ensure feasibility, improve computational efficiency, and capture the operational characteristics of commercial heat pump systems.

A. Thermal Model and Parameter Learning

To estimate indoor temperature dynamics for optimization, a simplified 1R1C thermal model is employed. The model represents the building as a thermal mass with heat capacity C , exchanging heat with the outdoor environment through a thermal resistance R . The continuous-time formulation is given by,

$$C \frac{dT_t^i}{dt} = \frac{T_t^o - T_t^i}{R} + COP \cdot P_t^h + Q_t^s \quad (7)$$

where the term $COP \cdot P_t^h$ denotes the thermal power delivered by the heat pump, expressed as the product of its electrical power consumption P_t^h and the associated coefficient of performance (COP). To support parameter learning and integration into the discrete-time optimization framework, the model is discretized as,

$$T_{t+1}^i = \alpha T_t^i + \beta(T_t^o - T_t^i) + \gamma P_t^h + \delta \quad (8)$$

The coefficients $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ in (8) are generally unknown and impractical to compute directly from the building envelope and heating system characteristics. Therefore, this paper proposes an automatic, data-driven approach to learn these parameters using a multiple linear regression model regularly trained on historical measurements. The parameter vector $\theta = [\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta]$ is obtained by minimizing the mean squared error between the predicted and actual indoor temperatures, defined as,

$$\min_{\theta} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N (T_{t+1}^{i,a} - T_{t+1}^{i,p}(\theta))^2 \quad (9)$$

where $T_{t+1}^{i,a}$ is the actual (measured) indoor temperature at time step $t+1$, $T_{t+1}^{i,p}(\theta)$ is the predicted temperature based on the estimated parameters θ of the model, and N is the total number of training samples. To ensure physical plausibility, the thermal inertia coefficient is constrained to $a \in [0,1]$. Furthermore, the model should be retrained regularly using a sliding time window of several days. Once trained and validated, it is used to predict indoor temperature in the optimization solution of Section III.B.

B. Proposed optimization solution

To overcome the limitations identified in the initial problem formulation of Section II, this section presents an enhanced and practical optimization approach. The proposed solution integrates the identified thermal model from Section III.A, replaces the hard thermal comfort constraints with soft constraints to ensure feasibility, excludes the non-essential complementarity constraints, and incorporates the operational characteristics of the heat pump.

In this direction, the objective function is modified to incorporate penalization of thermal limits violation, as,

$$\min \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} [\Delta T \cdot (c_t^i P_t^i - c_t^e P_t^e) + n \cdot \xi_t^n + z \cdot \xi_t^e] \quad (10)$$

where ξ_t^n and ξ_t^e are auxiliary variables representing violations of the normal and eco thermal limits, respectively, and n and z are the corresponding penalty coefficients. This penalization introduces thermal comfort as soft constraints, allowing controlled deviations from the predefined temperature bands without causing infeasibility when the indoor temperature falls outside the preferred range. Accordingly, the normal $[\underline{T}^n, \bar{T}^n]$ and eco $[\underline{T}^e, \bar{T}^e]$ comfort range are enforced through the following constraints.

$$\underline{T}^n - \xi_t^n \leq T_t^{i,p} \leq \bar{T}^n + \xi_t^n, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (11)$$

$$\underline{T}^e - \xi_t^e \leq T_t^{i,p} \leq \bar{T}^e + \xi_t^e, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12)$$

$$\xi_t^n \geq 0 \text{ and } \xi_t^e \geq 0 \quad (13)$$

With $z > n > 0$, higher penalties are applied for violations of the broader eco comfort range. This soft-constrained formulation provides flexibility under uncertain conditions

such as extreme weather or high electricity prices while maintaining occupant comfort and solution feasibility.

The non-convex complementarity constraint (2) of the initial problem statement is omitted in the proposed formulation. This is justified by the typical pricing structure in residential settings, where the import electricity price c_t^i is consistently higher than the export price c_t^e . Under such conditions, the optimization solution naturally avoids simultaneous import and export power to minimize cost, rendering the complementarity constraint unnecessary to improve the computational complexity without affecting solution correctness.

The indoor temperature T_t^i is estimated using the predicted value $T_t^{i,p}$ at each time t , as in (14), derived from the thermal model of (8) by using the trained parameters $\theta = [\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta]$ obtained via the regression process described in (9).

$$T_{t+1}^{i,p} = \alpha T_t^{i,p} + \beta(T_t^o - T_t^{i,p}) + \gamma P_t^h + \delta \quad (14)$$

It should be noted that the external temperature T_t^o over the prediction horizon \mathcal{T} can be obtained from third-party weather forecasting services based on the building's location. The accuracy of the predicted external temperature is of high importance as it can affect the decision-making process.

Finally, the technical operational characteristics of a commercial underfloor residential heating system have been analyzed, indicating that the heat pump is either deactivated or operating at its rated power. To reflect this behavior in the proposed formulation, a binary auxiliary variable $s_t \in \{0,1\}$ is introduced in (15) to represent the *on/off* state of the system.

$$P_t^h = s_t \cdot \bar{P}^h, \quad \forall t \quad (15)$$

The proposed optimization problem is formulated as an MILP, based on the updated objective function (10) and associated constraints (3), (11) - (15). The proposed solution, according to Section III.A and III.B, provides a practical, data-driven learning and MILP-based optimization framework. The solution is capable of minimizing electricity cost while preserving thermal comfort, enhancing feasibility through soft constraint handling, and relaxing non-essential constraints such as complementarity, in line with realistic heat pump and pricing behavior. Its performance is presented in Section IV.

IV. SIMULATION RESULT AND EVALUATION

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed learning and optimization solution, a simulation environment was developed in MATLAB/Simulink using the Simscape Thermal Library to accurately emulate the electrical and thermal behavior of a residential building. The simulation model was calibrated using power and indoor air temperature measurements from a residential building located in Nicosia, Cyprus. The building is equipped with a 5 kW rooftop photovoltaic (PV) system and an electricity-based underfloor heat pump system with 4 kW nominal electrical power and a coefficient of performance (COP) of 4.

In this investigation, the performance of the proposed data-driven thermal modeling is evaluated in Section IV.A, while the effectiveness of the optimization-based dynamic heat pump scheduling is assessed in Section IV.B. For comparison, two static time-scheduling scenarios are also considered: *Scenario A*, where the heat pump thermostat is always active, and *Scenario B*, where it is active daily from

Figure 1: Input data to the testing environment: (a) PV generation and load consumption; (b) variable import and export electricity prices.

16:00 to 24:00. In both static cases, when the thermostat is active, the heat pump turns *on* until the indoor temperature reaches the set-point of 23.5 °C and turns *off* once it drops 1 °C below (i.e., to 22.5 °C). In contrast, the proposed dynamic scheduling determines the *on/off* status based on the optimization solution from Section III.B, maintaining indoor temperature within a normal comfort band of 22.5 °C to 23.5 °C for fair comparison. The penalty weights for normal and eco comfort were set to 1 °C/€ and 5 °C/€, respectively, based on the guidance of [15], who recommend values between 1 and 10 to reflect different comfort priorities. These choices ensure consistency with existing literature and do not affect the optimization performance.

The case study examines the building operation over the period from February 6 to February 7, 2025. Historical PV generation and load consumption data were collected from the actual residential building in Nicosia and used as inputs to the testing environment, as shown in Figure 1(a). Additionally, time-varying import and export electricity prices for the same period were sourced from the pricing scheme implemented in Spain [16], shown in Figure 1(b), since variable electricity tariffs are not yet applied in Cyprus. These prices are announced the day before and are considered known a priori.

A. Evaluation of Thermal Model Learning

The performance of the learning algorithm in predicting indoor temperature was assessed under both static time-scheduling scenarios introduced earlier: Scenario A, where the heat pump thermostat controller is always active (Figure 2(a)), and Scenario B, where it is active daily from 16:00 to 24:00 (Figure 2(b)). Simulation data from January 31 to February 5, 2025, were used for training, with the following two days for testing. The 6-day period at 2-minute intervals yielded 4,320 temperature samples. Learning parameters from the fitting process and the regression accuracy performance indicators for the training and testing datasets based on Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination R^2 are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Training and Testing Parameters

Parameter/Indicators	Symbol	Unit	Value
Thermal Inertia Coef.	α	-	0.9978
Outdoor Temp. Coef.	β	-	0.0014
Heating Effic. Factor	γ	°C/kWh	0.0118
Training R^2	R^2_{Tr}	-	0.95
Training RMSE	$RMSE_{Tr}$	°C	0.13
Testing R^2	R^2_{Test}	-	0.92
Testing RMSE	$RMSE_{Test}$	°C	0.22

Figure 2 compares the actual and predicted indoor temperatures for both scenarios. In both cases, the predicted temperatures closely match the actual values, with a maximum deviation of 0.3 °C. These results confirm that the learned thermal model is sufficiently accurate to be integrated into the proposed dynamic optimization scheduling scheme.

Figure 2: Actual and predicted indoor temperature under two static time-scheduling scenarios considering (a) heat pump controller is always activated; and (b) heat pump controller is activated from 16:00 to 24:00.

B. Evaluation of Optimization-based Scheduling

A comparative analysis of heat pump power consumption and indoor temperature profiles is presented for both the optimized (dynamic scheduling) and non-optimized (static time-scheduling) approaches. Results for the always-activated thermostat scenario (Scenario A) are shown in Figure 3, while those for the limited 8-hour daily activation (Scenario B) are shown in Figure 4. These comparisons highlight clear differences in operational behavior, driven by the presence or absence of the proposed optimization strategy.

It is important to note that, prior to the two-day operating window shown in this section, the building was operated under the respective static scheduling strategy (Scenario A or B) for six consecutive days. During this period, the thermal model was trained based on the building's behavior, and the internal thermal states may differ between scenarios due to the distinct scheduling patterns.

In both scenarios (in Figure 3 and Figure 4), the dynamic scheduling scheme based on the proposed solution intelligently activates the heat pump during periods of low import prices or surplus export power. This behavior minimizes electricity costs while keeping indoor temperature mostly within the normal comfort range and always within the eco-comfort range. The result is a more cost-effective and comfort-aware heating operation. By contrast, the non-optimized approach relies solely on the thermostat controller and fixed time schedules, without accounting for electricity pricing. In Scenario A (Figure 3), where the thermostat is always active with a set-point of 23.5 °C, the system maintains the indoor temperature mostly within the 22.5 °C to 23.5 °C range, as the heat pump is activated at 22.5 °C and deactivated at 23.5 °C. In Scenario B (Figure 4), where the thermostat is active only from 16:00 to 24:00, the indoor temperature can drop below the comfort range (e.g., to 22 °C) during inactive

Figure 3: Comparison between dynamic (optimized) scheduling and static (non-optimized) scheduling when thermostat is always activated, considering (a) heating power consumption and (b) indoor temperature.

Figure 4: Comparison between dynamic (optimized) scheduling and static scheduling when thermostat is activated between 16:00 and 24:00, considering (a) heating power consumption and (b) indoor temperature.

hours. Such deviations may become more pronounced on colder days due to limited control flexibility.

To quantify the impact of these variations, the average absolute Indoor Thermal Comfort Index (TCI) was calculated for each case. The TCI reflects the mean deviation of indoor temperature from a target comfort value, set to 23 °C which reflect the middle of the comfort zone in both dynamic and static scenarios. Additionally, total electricity cost was computed for each scheduling strategy. Results are presented in Table 2. In both scenarios, the optimized dynamic scheduling achieves lower temperature deviations (e.g., 0.24 °C and 0.20 °C vs. 0.43 °C and 0.62 °C for Scenarios A and B, respectively) and reduced electricity costs (15.20 € and 16.14 € vs. 16.72 € and 17.12 €). These findings confirm the effectiveness of the proposed framework in improving both comfort and economic performance.

Table 2: TCI and electricity cost

Scheduling approach	Scenario A: Heat pump controller always activated	
	Average TCI (°C)	Total Electricity Cost (€)
Optimized	0.24	15.20
Non-Opt.	0.43	16.72
Scheduling approach	Scenario B: Heat pump controller activated for 8 hours	
	Average TCI (°C)	Total Electricity Cost (€)
Optimized	0.20	16.14
Non-Opt.	0.62	17.12

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposed a combined data-driven thermal modeling and optimization-based energy management framework for residential buildings, aimed at minimizing electricity costs while maintaining occupant comfort. The proposed learning approach enables accurate prediction of indoor temperatures using minimal sensor data, without requiring detailed knowledge of the building's physical characteristics. Additionally, the optimization-based dynamic scheduling scheme enhances cost-effectiveness and thermal comfort, while improving feasibility and computational efficiency. A calibrated simulation environment based on real building measurements was used to validate the proposed solution compared to two static scheduling scenarios. Results show a 6-10% reduction in electricity cost and a 45-68%

improvement in thermal comfort compared to static, pre-defined scheduling strategies.

Future work will enhance the framework's robustness, scalability, and applicability. Optimization and learning models will be extended to multi-zone buildings, capturing thermal effects and zone-specific comfort needs. Simulations will include multiple seasons, varied building thermal properties, and long-term economic evaluations to enhance generalizability. In addition, performance comparison with other rule- or optimization-based existing solutions will be conducted to highlight the benefits of the proposed solution.

Furthermore, sensitivity analysis will be performed to assess the impact of subjective weight coefficients and to complement the current literature-based justification. Moreover, stochastic optimization or MPC approaches will be explored to address weather forecasting or modelling errors and improve solution accuracy.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. L. Li, M. Y. Han, S. Y. Liu, and G. Q. Chen, "Energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions by buildings: A multi-scale perspective," *Building and Environment*, vol. 151, pp. 240–250, 2019.
- [2] F. Bre and V. D. Fachinotti, "A computational multi-objective optimization method to improve energy efficiency and thermal comfort in dwellings," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 154, pp. 283–294, 2017.
- [3] P. H. Shaikh, et al., "Intelligent multi-objective optimization for building energy and comfort management," *J. King Saud Univ.–Eng. Sci.*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 195–204, 2018.
- [4] A. Berouine, et al., "A predictive control approach for thermal energy management in buildings," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 9127–41, 2022.
- [5] S. Zhan, et al., "Data requirements and performance evaluation of model predictive control in buildings: A modeling perspective," *Renewable Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 142, p. 110835, 2021.
- [6] L. Di Natale, et al., "Towards scalable physically consistent neural networks: An application to data-driven multi-zone thermal building models," *Applied Energy*, vol. 340, p. 121071, Jun. 2023.
- [7] X. Xin, et al., "A comprehensive review of predictive control strategies in heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC): Model-free vs model," *J. Building Eng.*, vol. 72, p. 110013, 2024.
- [8] Z. Guo, X. Zhu, Y. Li, and Y. Wu, "Aggregation and data driven identification of building thermal dynamic model and unmeasured disturbance," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 231, p. 110500, Jan. 2021.
- [9] W. Belazi, et al., "Thermal modeling of the occupied multi-zone buildings taking into account the uncertainties of occupant behavior," *Case Stud. Thermal Eng.*, vol. 33, p. 101978, May 2022.
- [10] S. Taheri, P. Hosseini, and A. Razban, "Model predictive control of heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems: A state-of-the-art review," *J. Building Eng.*, vol. 60, p. 105067, 2022.
- [11] G. Bianchini, et al., "An integrated model predictive control approach for optimal HVAC and energy storage operation in large-scale buildings," *Applied Energy*, vol. 240, pp. 327–340, Apr. 2019.
- [12] R. Eini and S. Abdelwahed, "Distributed model predictive control based on goal coordination for multi-zone building temperature control," in *Proc. IEEE GreenTech*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [13] S. Thorsteinnsson, et al., "Long-term experimental study of price responsive predictive control in a real occupied single-family house with heat pump," *Applied Energy*, vol. 347, p. 121398, 2023.
- [14] S. Schmitz, K. Brucke, P. Kasturi, E. Ansari, and P. Klement, "Forecast-based and data-driven reinforcement learning for residential heat pump operation," *Applied Energy*, vol. 371, p. 123688, Jan. 2024.
- [15] H. Qin, Z. Yu, T. Li, X. Liu, and L. Li, "Heating control strategy based on dynamic programming for building energy saving and emission reduction," *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 21, p. 14137, 2022.
- [16] Red Eléctrica de España, "Electricity demand analysis – December 4, 2024," *ESIOS*, Available: <https://www.esios.ree.es/en/analysis/1739>